

CHARACTERISATION OF DAMAGE IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES USING LINE FOCUS ACOUSTIC MICROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT

Line focus acoustic microscopy has been used to measure the Rayleigh wave velocity of a particle reinforced metal matrix composite at a series of positions within the necked region of a failed tensile specimen. The Rayleigh wave velocity of a material is simply related to its density, Poisson's ratio and shear modulus. We have compared our measurements of a 5% by volume SiC reinforced commercial purity Al matrix composite with predicted reductions in the Rayleigh wave velocity as determined using Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method to relate particle damage to changes in elastic properties.

INTRODUCTION

The fracture behaviour of particle reinforced metal matrix composites (PRMMC), and that of other MMCs with discontinuous reinforcements, shows features characteristic of matrix ductile rupture. In these materials ductile fracture follows the same sequence of void nucleation, void growth, and void coalescence at failure as is seen with monolithic metals. The condition that leads to void nucleation at particles embedded in ductile metals has been the subject of study for a number of years. In PRMMC materials void nucleation can occur either by the fracture of the reinforcing particles or by decohesion at the particle matrix interface. The conditions which lead to the selection of nucleation mechanism in a particular PRMMC system are complex and are a function of matrix chemistry and reinforcement concentration, size and shape. In general systems containing large reinforcing particles fail by fracture and those with small particles fail by decohesion. Also, as the strength of the matrix material increases, there is an increased tendency for particle fracture to be the dominant void nucleation mechanism.

In ductile metals during tensile straining void nucleation is believed to occur in a burst after some critical strain [1]. If this were also true in PRMMCs, the very high density of void nucleation sites would lead to little ductility after the initial nucleation event because the high density of voids should lead to rapid coalescence. However, acoustic emission studies [2] indicate that in PRMMCs there is no sudden burst of void nucleation and instead continuous void nucleation occurs throughout plastic deformation after a small critical plastic strain for the onset of nucleation. Thus, plastic deformation of PRMMCs leads to a continuous accumulation of damage until some critical level of damage results in failure. The characterisation of damage prior to failure is an important aspect of research in MMCs. There have been a number of techniques used in the past including: optical examination of cross-sectioned specimens after failure [3], continuum damage methods when a bulk property of the material (e.g. density, stiffness or Poisson's ratio) is monitored as a function of strain [4,5,6,7]. Acoustic emissions can be detected from MMCs soon after plastic straining [2] and this too can be used to monitor the processes prior to failure. Finally X-ray microtomography has been used to measure materials density in the necked region of failed tensile specimens as a technique to assess damage [8] In this paper we present a new technique for the characterisation of damage in MMCs using line focus acoustic microscopy.

PRMMC DAMAGE CHARACTERISATION TECHNIQUES

It is well known that non-catastrophic failure of the reinforcement often occurs during the straining of composite materials and that this results in a reduction of the bulk elastic modulus. The monitoring of reductions in elastic modulus during straining is a common tool for the characterisation of damage and it has been used extensively in studies of damage evolution in long fibre reinforced polymer matrix systems both during tensile straining and after fatigue loading. The technique has also been used by a number of workers in the field of particle reinforced metal matrix composites. Damage is defined using the conventional continuum formulation

$$D = 1 - \frac{E}{E_0} \quad (1)$$

where D is the damage parameter, E is the elastic modulus of the composite measured at a given plastic strain and E_0 is the elastic modulus at zero plastic strain, taken as the reference undamaged state. The observed relationship between elastic modulus damage and plastic strain is non-linear and there is no obvious correlation between particle size or volume fraction of reinforcement and the damaged state at a given strain.

Mochida *et al* [9] have used the Eshelby equivalent inclusion technique to correlate modulus reduction damage measurements with the number of fractured particles. However it is impossible to decouple the number of failed particles from the total volume of voids present and in order to simplify the calculation it is necessary to assume that all the voids have the same aspect ratio and size. Another serious limitation of all mechanical models used to interpret the results of elastic modulus reduction measured during tensile testing occurs is that the models cannot decouple the increase in compliance caused by specimen section change (necking) from any damage related compliance change. Thus, these techniques, although very simple to carry out, are difficult to analyse in detail and at best produce only a qualitative measure of damage. Also, because of the volume averaging inherent in the measurements made, it is difficult to use the technique to study the growth and coalescence of voids which leads to final bulk failure.

It is possible to investigate the nucleation and growth of voids prior to failure by examining cross-sectioned specimens after failure either using an optical microscope or a scanning electron microscope. Measurements of the local void volume and number of failed reinforcing particles can be made from such cross-sections. Damage can be defined as the fraction of fractured or damaged particles, or from the reduction in material density.

$$D = 1 - N/N_0 \quad (2)$$

$$D = 1 - \rho/\rho_0 \quad (3)$$

where N and ρ are the number of undamaged particles and the material density after a given strain and the subscript 0 indicates the equivalent undamaged state. However, making these measurements is a tedious process and is probably impractical for any study investigating a large number of specimens. If the observation is made on or near the specimen surface the deformation state is in plane stress whereas that in the specimen bulk is closer to plane strain. This difference in deformation state can lead to different estimates of damage evolution [10]. It can also be very difficult to accurately determine whether a particle is cracked if there has been very little crack opening. We have extended this technique by using X-ray tomography to reconstruct the density of voids present within a specimen below a fracture surface [8]. X-ray tomography and its applications in materials science have been covered extensively in recent reviews [11]. Unfortunately Al and SiC have very similar X-ray absorption coefficients (6.77cm^{-1} and 7.58cm^{-1} respectively), hence it is not possible to distinguish density differences caused by local changes in reinforcement distribution from those caused by very small void concentrations. Nonetheless it provides an excellent tool to monitor void growth handicapped by the very long time (several hours) needed to characterise each specimen.

Acoustic emission (AE), the propagation of transient elastic waves within a material by sudden local displacements, occurs during the fracture of a reinforcing particle within a PRMMC. The transient elastic waves are detected at the specimen surface by piezoelectric transducers. The amplitude of the surface displacements and hence their detectability is a function of the size of

the AE event in terms of the displaced volume and its speed of motion. AE monitoring can be used to characterise the reinforcement failure events during tensile testing [2]. Each AE event is believed to indicate a particle failure event and thus it can be used to measure a damage parameter similar to equation 3. AE monitoring is one of the few measurements of damage evolution which can be truly carried out *in situ* during testing. It appears to give an excellent measure of damage nucleation but of course it can give no further information of damage evolution such as void growth. A further limitation of this technique is its volume averaging nature. The entire gauge length is sampled and serious miscounting may occur once strain localisation (necking) occurs prior to final fracture. It may be possible to account for this by measuring time of flight between two transducers to give spatial information about the acoustic source.

Finally it is possible to make measurements of changes in specimen density (picnometry) after straining as a measure of damage [5]. This also requires the measurement of relatively large volumes of material (some mm³) to improve reliability and thus suffers from the problem of volume averaging common to many of the other techniques.

In summary, there are a large number of experimental techniques with which it is possible to characterise microstructural damage within a PRMMC. The only techniques which can be used to measure the development of damage within the necked region of a tensile specimen are those based on imaging the damaged microstructure, i.e. the direct metallographic observation of specimen surfaces or polished cross-sections, and tomographic reconstruction. Of these the use of cross-sections is limited if the cracked particle show little opening and X-ray tomography is currently very slow if laboratory X-ray sources are used. Techniques such as picnometry and elastic modulus reduction, although they are rapid and sample damage at all size scales, are handicapped by their volume average nature.

LINE FOCUS ACOUSTIC MICROSCOPY

We have used a line focusing acoustic microscope (LFM) to characterise failed PRMMC specimens in the necked region. This instrument produces line-source cylindrical waves rather than the usual spherical waves, which allows the measurement of anisotropic acoustic properties as a function of lens orientation. Figure 1 shows a schematic outline of the microscope, the cylindrical acoustic lens produces acoustic waves in the frequency range of a few hundred MHz. These are coupled with the specimen using a water droplet and generate surface Rayleigh waves. By operating in a pulse-echo mode the lens can also be used to detect the Rayleigh waves. It is thus possible to characterise a material by analysis of the amplitude of the induced Rayleigh waves. A full description of the LFM and the analysis of the theory outlined above can be found

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the line focus acoustic microscope. A cylindrical lens is coupled with the specimen surface and generates Rayleigh waves normal to the cylinder axis.

Figure 2. $V(z)$ curve measured using a line focus acoustic microscope.

Figure 3. Rayleigh wave velocity measured in the necked region of a failed 5% V_f 30 μm SiC particle reinforced metal matrix composite.

in the work of Kushibiki and Cubachi [12]. A complete description of the instrument constructed for this work can be found in the work of Lawrence [13].

The acoustic microscope can be used to characterise materials by analysis of the acoustic materials signature $V(z)$. A plot of the output (V) of an acoustic lens as a function of the lens separation (z) is shown in figure 2. In the samples analysed $V(z)$ took the form of a maximum at focus ($z = 0$) and an approximately exponentially decreasing sine wave at negative defocus. The Rayleigh wave velocity (v_R) of the surface being characterised may be determined from the distance between the peaks in the $V(z)$ trace [12]. Rayleigh waves are largely shear in nature and the following semi-empirical relation used by Scruby and Drain [13] relates the Rayleigh wave velocity to the shear wave velocity (v_s):

$$v_s = (1.14418 - 0.25771\nu + 0.126617\nu^2)v_R \tag{4}$$

where ν is the Poisson ratio of the material. The shear modulus (G) can be calculated using the relation

$$G = v_s^2 \rho \quad (5)$$

where ρ is the density of the material. These equations assume the material to be elastically isotropic which is not correct for the damaged composite but is probably a reasonable approximation.

The LFM was used to characterise the necked region in a failed tensile specimen of a 5% by volume 30 μm SiC particle reinforced commercial purity aluminium. A frequency of 225 MHz was used for the measurements of $V(z)$. We measured $V(z)$ curves with the axis of the lens perpendicular to the tensile axis of the specimen to maximise spatial resolution. The line focus was produced by a cylindrical lens, is 1.73mm in length and samples a width of approximately 100 μm . Figure 3 shows the measured Rayleigh wave velocity as a function of distance from the fracture surface. The distance from the fracture surface can be converted into a strain by measuring the area reduction at each position sampled. The microstructural damage can be quantified by using equations 1 and 2 to determine the change in shear modulus in the necked region.

Figure 4. Representation of the microstructure modeled by Mochida *et al* [9] showing the replacement of the damaged reinforcement particles by a region of matrix containing a penny shaped crack.

Both shear modulus and Poisson's ratio control the Rayleigh wave velocity and thus a mechanical model of the influence of damage on all elastic properties is required. Mochida *et al* [9] have used the Eshelby equivalent inclusion method to determine the elastic modulus of a damaged PRMMC using a simple model in which the broken particles are replaced by an equivalent volume of matrix material containing a penny shaped crack (figure 4). Using their approach the compliance tensor of the damaged composite has been determined. With a 5% volume fraction PRMMC the Poisson ratio is fairly insensitive to damage but there is significant reduction in the shear modulus. Rewriting equations 4 and 5

Figure 5. Normalised Rayleigh wave data from figure 3.

Figure 6. Rayleigh wave velocity calculated using equation 6 and modeled elastic properties in a 5% volume fraction SiC reinforced Al PRMMC

$$v_R = \frac{1}{1.14418 - 0.25771\nu + 0.12661\nu^2} \sqrt{\frac{G}{\rho}} \quad (6)$$

shows that the Rayleigh wave velocity is only a weak function of Poisson's ratio and the effects of the reduction in shear modulus and density expected during damage evolution will, to some extent, cancel each other out. The change in Rayleigh wave velocity seen in figure 3 is normalised by the velocity of undamaged material and replotted in figure 5. The maximum reduction in velocity is only 2% just below the fracture surface. This data is now compared with

the predicted reduction in Rayleigh wave velocity using the Eshelby type model for the change in shear modulus and Poisson's ratio as shown in figure 6. The very small changes in Rayleigh wave velocity measured by the LFM are clearly consistent with the level of damage expected in these materials when compared with values in the literature.

CONCLUSIONS

The conditions for void nucleation in metal matrix composites are still an area for considerable research. The ductile failure process in particle reinforced metal matrix composites has been characterised using a number of techniques. Conventional methods of damage characterisation which are used to measure void growth rates during tensile fracture are limited by poor spatial resolution. Line Focus Acoustic Microscopy has been used to characterise damage in an example PRMMC system. The results can be interpreted using Eshelby type models of mechanical behaviour and are shown to be consistent with other measurements in the literature. The technique shows considerable promise as a tool for damage characterisation which may have applications in the general field of ductile fracture and not just for metal matrix composites.

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